

SHARED VALUE AS A CONTRIBUTOR TO SOCIAL INNOVATION

Case study: The Universidad de los Andes and its surrounding entrepreneurial environment.

María de los Ángeles González Pérez
Associate Professor, Universidad de los Andes – Team Member, Emprende Program
✉ marigonz@uniandes.edu.co

Freddy Zapata Vanegas
Associate Professor, Universidad de los Andes – Team Member, Emprende Program
✉ fzapata@uniandes.edu.co

Javier Francisco Silva Salazar
Methodological Advisor – Team Member, Emprende Program
✉ blife@busineslifemodel.com

Santiago Restrepo Barrera
Methodological Advisor – Team Member, Emprende Program

ABSTRACT

The creation of networks involving different stakeholders in a community promotes an ideal environment for the development of shared value towards social innovation. The *Emprende* Program is a course targeting 16 neighborhood businesses which are connected with the Universidad de los Andes, Bogotá. Among other objectives, the program aims to develop entrepreneurial skills such as problem identification, risk taking and team work. Such skills respond to changes in urban landscapes and challenges from new competitors.

The program's methodologies combine analytical and design thinking. The program consisted of sessions that involved participatory work, observation, creativity, and management. Prototype development is an integrative mechanism for team work, network creation, and the skills appropriation skills. All of these aspects are key to the development of shared value and the fostering of social innovation.

Finally, the program fostered skills among small-scale entrepreneurs and enabled them to transform their practice, thus promoting the creation of social capital by instilling deeper levels of awareness both of their own roles and of their environments.

KEY WORDS: *shared value, social innovation, social networks, business model, design thinking.*

INTRODUCTION

The Progresia Fenicia Project and the Emprende Program

By observing and identifying the results of behaviors and interactions among individuals and communities involved in projects aimed at fostering innovation, entrepreneurship and competition, the program moves the discussion beyond questions of science and technology, becoming a laboratory for testing actions that lead to social innovation.

In social innovation, solutions to problems do not lie only in the production and accumulation of wealth. The key re-

sides in fact in creating sustainable changes in people's lives (Juarez, 2009). For the *Emprende* Program¹, these changes also involve companies and organizations creating shared value by making connections that are capable of enhancing the performance of individuals within communities, contributing in this way to economic, social, environmental, and geopolitical development.

The *Las Aguas* neighborhood of Bogotá D.C, in which the Universidad de los Andes is located, is of great significance

1. **Translator's note:** the Spanish word *Emprende* is a second person imperative of the verb *emprender*. In this context it conveys the idea of encouraging individuals or companies to develop as entrepreneurs.

for the development of the city center; the neighborhood is, in addition, part of an urban renewal project. The *Progresía Fenicia* project was created under the leadership of the Universidad de los Andes in response to these circumstances in the area of *Las Aguas* known as the *Triángulo de Fenicia*. Its objective is to develop projects that have a high impact on the surrounding space and to encourage transformation, innovation, and sustainability in the area.

The project operates according to three strategic priorities:

- People as stakeholders and subjects of transformation.
- Activities (i.e., work, production, sales) carried out in the zone as engines of change and to improve living conditions.
- Urban landscapes emerging from public and private spaces to ensure the interaction of interests and the creation of collective identity.

Emprende emerged in 2012 on the initiative of *Progresía Fenicia*'s leadership group, with the objective of promoting entrepreneurial activities in the area. The main goal was to improve the economic and social conditions of small businesses in the vicinity of the university by following an approach that was intended to empower businesses to adopt more productive and innovative practices.

Among the achievements expected of the small-scale entrepreneurs were: the ability to identify new opportunities and solve problems affecting their businesses; create spaces for collaborative creation (co-creation) where each could share their experiences and learning; and develop teamworking abilities which would enable them to make good decisions, take risks, develop communication skills and take ownership of ideas, concepts, and processes.

Based on these practices for better entrepreneurship, the project sought to develop efficient business models organized according to three axes: new value propositions, understanding customer needs and business strengthening to ensure long term sustainability. Tools including observation, creativity, and management were applied in practical exercises with entrepreneurs, alongside theoretical concepts, thus promoting interaction and value creation.

The program was developed through three modules:

- The first module, “Yes, I have a product and a client”, focused on developing and consolidating the entrepreneurial project by emphasizing product delivery and interaction between entrepreneurs and customers.
- The second, called “Yes, I have a business”, focused on the importance of entrepreneurs understanding their own business model: efficient intake and output of resources, and understanding of process flow (the value chain).
- The last module, “Yes, I am sustainable” sought to secure the sustainability businesses through the formalization in long term and establishment of strategic partnerships.

32 small-scale entrepreneurs from 16 neighborhood businesses participated in the first phase of the program².

2. 7 restaurants, 4 copying and Internet venues, 1 store, 1 supermarket, 1 hospice, and 1 woodshop.

The program team consisted of professionals from the faculties of Administration, Architecture and Design at the Universidad de los Andes. In the beginning, the concept of creating shared value was not explicit either for the entrepreneurs or the university staff. The concept became visible during the course, which consequently achieved more than had originally been foreseen when its objectives were set. The initial situation created an ideal environment for generating knowledge and envisioning broader horizons for the social and economic components of the businesses involved in the project, introducing the concept of shared value to the community and to its productive activities.

THE EMPRENDE PROGRAM AND SHARED VALUE

The creation of networks, here understood as the promotion of partnerships between different stakeholders in the same community, promotes the development of shared value. As argued by Porter & Kramer (2011, p.5) “Shared value creation focuses on identifying and expanding the connections between societal and economic progress. In addition to reconceiving the interaction between society and corporate performance”.

From its inception, *Emprende* has sought to impact on each of the stakeholders, in addition to promoting deeper social interactions between them by encouraging the performance of tangible and intangible economic activities. These activities contributed to the creation of new value networks as a result of the shared experiences of stakeholders. Porter & Kramer (2011, p. 5) identify three key ways in which companies can create shared value by: “reconceiving products and markets, redefining productivity in the value chain, and building supportive industry clusters at the company’s locations”. From this perspective, *Emprende* fulfills the task of giving entrepreneurs basic guidelines regarding these concepts, while proposing changes in their thinking as individuals and developing a collective, community-oriented mindset.

The first module enabled the entrepreneurs to consider and act upon the needs and benefits concerning their value proposal from different perspectives. This new way of thinking about products, services and customers had a great impact on the stakeholders from the business environment.

The second module prompted understanding and conceptualization of a value chain and helped define added value in products and services by identifying the characteristics of market sectors and profiles. It thus provided entrepreneurs with guidelines for understanding and helped them re-think and model new proposals.

Finally, the third module envisioned opportunities for developing local clusters by building on the skills and networks developed by small-scale entrepreneurs. While such skills and networks did not exist at the beginning of the program, they came to represent a potential space for the creation of shared value.

We took the findings and difficulties that emerged during our work with the businesses as references to validate the concept of shared value within the program. In addition, we sought to establish a range of relationships, encouraging the development of internal networks within the work teams and external ones between entrepreneurs and the university.

INTERNAL NETWORKS AND DESIGN THINKING

A network is a strategic mechanism which integrates individuals and actions under a structure of interests, trust, and reciprocity (Becerra, 2008). Networks involve learning and innovation. As Tracy and Clack, 2003 (cited in Becerra, 2008) have pointed out, networks promote interactive learning in organizations through the sharing of knowledge and information, permitting the construction of values and new work models.

The development of networks is the product of the relation between two principal kinds of opportunity that promote the development of networks: first, a driver which motivates collaboration during the development of social capital and, second, interventions intended to act on restrictions or voids, which create opportunities for establishing new connections (Galaskiewicz y Wasserman 1981; Meriden, 1985; Kogut et al., 1994, cited by Walker, 1997).

Innovation creates differential value in relation to existing situations. It should thus be understood as a systematic process involving complementary acts of integration between people, elements, and actions. In the case of *Emprende*, we integrated innovation into a methodology based on design thinking, emphasizing in particular the creative nature of every part of the process. Thus, analytical and design thinking were integrated, both becoming mutually complementary. While scientists research phenomena in order to discover elements and patterns, designers create new patterns and concepts, which make it easier to deal with new possibilities (Owen, 2006). In addition, design thinking leads to innovation that is centered on people and experiences, creating new relationship systems and cultivating a cutting edge culture and processes based on discipline in which, as Kumar (2013) argues,

individuals draw on real life situations, observing, iterating³ and learning from them.

Observing, iterating, and learning are key aspects of the creative process because groups need to gain experience and knowledge through hypothesis-testing focused on problem solving⁴.

In practice, design thinking revolves around two axes, discussed by Beckman and Barry (2007). One is based on the interplay between the rational and the practical, another moves between the real and abstract. These axes inform the development of the four stages of design thinking: the first stage as Discovering, the second stage as Interpreting, the third stage as Deciding, and the fourth stage as Solving.

Emprende's methodology applies the principles of design thinking to all three of the modules discussed above (Figure 1). Negotiating the four stages means that planning must involve processes of both divergent and convergent thought. Divergent thought works with creative, unstructured processes that involve a high level of uncertainty. Convergent thought works with processes which are analytical, rational, and synthesis oriented (Owen, 2005 y Beckman & Barry, 2007).

The first and the second stages make reference to the observation module (see Figure 2). Jointly with the entrepreneurs we identified aspects that were specific to their respective businesses: their product and/or service and the market. Similarly, entrepreneurs were presented with potential future scenarios, which allowed them to envision a “rational business

3. Martin (2006) describes abductive reasoning as a process of modeling an exploratory hypothesis as the only logical operation likely to introduce new ideas. Martin cites Pierce (1905, in turn cited by Hoffman, 1995).
4. According to Dunne & Martin (2006) this aspect relates to abductive thought, responding in a creative and propositional manner to restrictive situations. This aspect is advantageous in processes. That is, traditional inductive and deductive thinking are integrated within it, as inductive thinking generalizes from a specific case, while deductive thinking makes inferences based on logical premises.

Figure 1. Program Modules and Method for Design Thinking

Figure 2. Design thinking methodology—stages and modules

model”⁵. These models included tangible brand concepts that were tested by developing small-scale “prototypes”, tested in the classroom and in business premises before being tested out on a larger scale.

The results of this business model inscribed the individual ideas of each business based on their knowledge and experience. This model did not prove to be very much different from the other proposals for value in similar businesses.

The second and third stages were directed toward the creative module creation. Results were analyzed according to the model of “creative and strategic business” (see Figure 3). The “creative business model” uses divergent thinking to envision the rational business model from divergent and novel perspectives

5. Rational business model (descriptive model of information and understanding of the processes that currently occur in the business), creative business model (divergent iteration model that facilitates obtaining answers and unexpected items, hard to find using conventional conservative and dynamic processes) and strategic business model (converged business model, test results information of the predecessor models, which allows the user/entrepreneur to obtain differentiating findings and results for execution time).

The rational, creative and strategic business models are part of the methodology used in the course “Product 4 (Product strategy)”, taught by the Design program at the Universidad de los Andes.

in order to gain differentiation and create value within the multiple aspects which make up the business environment.

Results were analyzed according of “the creative and strategic business model” (see Figure 3). The creative Business model tool uses divergent thinking to envision the rational business model from divergent and novel perspectives in order to gain differentiation and create value within the multiple aspects which make up the business environment.

The strategic business model emerges as a result of this process. It responds to the dynamics of convergent thinking and rational and structured business logic, without losing the advantageous aspects of the creative model.

The third and fourth stages were associated with management and demonstration modules. The creative outcomes with small-scale entrepreneurs and potential partners became more visible during these stages. Outcomes were presented to a group of experts and professionals (Events 1 & 2) in order to obtain their feedback on the value proposals, curves, service mapping and routes, and service experiences within the different businesses.

Feedback gathered during these events set the scene for each of the *Emprende Program* modules that were introduced subsequently. These operated according to established timelines for the development of sessions, workshops, and assignments.

Figure 3. Types of business models in the methodology

Prototype value and network building

When it is applied, design thinking takes into account the principles of interdisciplinary work, uncertainty, and complexity. Building prototypes as a strategy enabled us to address these principles and also to build networks and work teams; which contributed to the development and management of the program.

In the classroom, we implemented workshops for developing prototypes intended to help consolidate businesses. For this purpose we used the Business Life (BL) tool. This tool, which is designed to visualize information and concepts, allowed us to organize the workshop components and establish relations between them in creative ways, thus facilitating novel business strategies and configurations.

The dynamic of the workshops using the BL tool (see Figure 4) promoted interactions between people, relying on their particular skills and knowledge. Hence, from the initial definition of the prototype⁶ we developed and co-created proposals emerging from the creative model while in the creative and management dimensions we used the strategic model.

The workshop results were enhanced with support from the work team and students from the Design and Administration faculties. The students joined the program during its third stage, contributing to the development of the prototypes and the differentiation of proposals, which were implemented in a project that integrated academic work and everyday business. As entrepreneur Sanchez, owner of the restaurant *Me rotacos*, affirmed:

“Confidence (...) was key (...): knowing that the program was not just teaching me a traditional course, but that they were in my establishment, observing my work and my shortcomings”. Daza,

6. Here, understood as the design of a work model intending to test product and service concepts associated with relationships between customers and suppliers.

C. (producer) (2013). *Closing Video for Emprende*. Bogota: Media Workshop, Architecture and Design faculty.

With regards to the rational, creative, and strategic business models we implemented, we worked with prototypes and pilots, including typologies such as: entry tests, fast prototypes, concept testing and association pilots, all of which are discussed by Murray, R. Caulier-Grice, J. & Mulgan, G. (2010).

Based on the prototypes developed within the creative dimension, we drew on the value proposal developed in collaboration with the individual entrepreneur during observation. The value proposals were initially developed on the basis of the rational business model, organized according to the components, which individual entrepreneurs identified as relevant to their business from a logical and foundational perspective. The entrepreneurs received support from the team during the analysis and inventory process; this exercise was framed within entry tests prototyping typology.

Figure 4. The Business Life Model Tool

For the creative business model we used concept prototypes that promoted creativity (see photo 1). During this exercise we observed the ways in which the entrepreneurs understood the rational model based on new interpretations of images (collage?) thus identifying relationships and narratives, which had not previously been noticed. Such was the case of a business called, the *Casetica de la Esquina* (the Corner Hut), where two young women managed to project their business towards different areas of the market, transforming themselves from street vendors into a specialized business selling necessities for university women⁸.

The prototypes were intended to provide a sense of psychological freedom and security⁹. The workshop provided an environment, which was not influenced by external judgments that might have inhibited the free expression of participants' proposals. As Landau argues (1987), such an environment of acceptance and trust strengthens bonds of friendship and empathy. Project members Beltrán, J., Londoño, S., Neira, C. & Raffo, A. expressed this as follows in their report on their work with entrepreneurs (13 December de 2013):

"We kept in permanent contact with the owners of Shawarma. That was our greatest achievement in making their ideas concrete. We believe this is essential for co-creation. Developing a friendship with entrepreneurs helped us create empathy and increase the flow of ideas and team productivity".

The entrepreneurs began the program with the expectation of transforming their businesses and, since motivation is a key driver of the creativity required to meet unsatisfied needs, this enabled an effective creative model to be developed. Finally, fast prototypes and association pilots were developed for the Management and Demonstration axes, as a means of achieving a strategic business model. Fast prototypes required immediate implementation capable of speeding up the learning process and possible applications of the new ideas (Murray, R., Caulier-Grice, J. & Mulgan, G., 2010). In this case, the entrepreneurs absorbed the theoretical model in a natural and spontaneous way. Activities focused on the aspects of identity and branding (logo, packaging, service goals and design of interior spaces). In their report Beltrán, J., Londoño, S., Neira, C. & Raffo, A. (13 de December of 2013) added:

"The San Isidro practice experience demonstrates the importance of establishing the role of the designer within a co-creation exercise. Development by entrepreneurs of their prototype was very autonomous, and our work consisted mainly in guiding them through the process with very minor contributions".

7. A creative technique of registering and visualizing using image clippings and random headlines from newspapers and magazines; its purpose is to create new narratives and imaginaries.
8. Value proposal: "The *Casetica de la Esquina* offers products for basic care, targeting young women who want immediate well-being solutions on a daily basis. We also provide accessories, beauty products, diet snacks and candy for healthy cravings", Universidad de los Andes, 2013.
9. Understanding psychological freedom as an attitude that enables individuals to playfully manage perceptions, concepts, and meanings; whereas, security is achieved through self-confidence and acceptance (Landau, 1987).

Photo 1. Creative Business Model

Photo 2. Strategic Business Model. Event 1: Value proposal

Photo 3. Strategic Business Model. Event 1: Communication skills

Fast prototypes enabled us to envision and realize better practices for consolidating the strategic business model, which culminated with the demonstrations in Event 1: value proposal and Event 2: potential partners (see photos 2, 3, 4 and 5).

For their part, *association pilots* were conducted with larger scale prototypes. Through visualizations created using the BL tool, we were able to enhance the value proposal of each business model and its most representative and important components. These components were not only realized through identity and branding, but also in products and service experiences.

In this program, we built shared value through the identification of needs and challenges for the development of both the Universidad de los Andes and the community. Here, people are the motivation and engine of social innovation, through their interactions, just as human centered design is to design thinking.

Though internal networks focused on consolidating the practices of the program within each business's team, the concept of external networks plays a role in the interaction with actors outside of the university.

EXTERNAL NETWORKS AND THE COMMUNITY

An external network involves stakeholders from outside the organization or institution. These networks constitute processes that seek to integrate and facilitate communication between different members of the community; organizations and institutions are the main frame of reference.

During the execution of the program we identified two types of external networks:

1. *Vertical external networks*¹⁰ connected with the university. These emerged from actions that prompted the development of new spaces for the stakeholders involved in the process. They maintained the mutually beneficial relationships created as a result of the process by implementing new dynamics, which strengthen specific interests.
2. *Horizontal external networks*¹¹ created between other members of the community. These are bonds established between businesses, employees, suppliers, residents and customers in order to develop new actions and behaviors, which generate mutual benefit and help businesses, become more competitive as they enter a differential environment. Strategic partnerships enabled the growth of entrepreneurial structures by developing new ways of thinking and interacting (Canel & Mitchell, 2013). For instance, since business owners in the community knew each other, there was a sense of belonging in the community, which provided opportunities for sharing experienc-

10. Those modes of cooperation between companies that are situated in different and consecutive positions within the production chain, aiming to reach competitive advantages they could not achieve individually. The most common example is the establishment of a partnership of strategic stable supply between various client micro and medium companies and their networks and subcontractors and suppliers (Becerra 2008, p. 39).

11. A mode of cooperation between independent companies of comparable size, which produce the same type of goods and decide to join forces in order to market them, buy supplies collectively, or procure common services; or companies that organize together in order to produce a unique product, each of them specializing in different parts and components. Usually, these networks are mainly oriented towards scale economies and greater negotiating power, and they are often made of groups of micro, small, and medium sized companies operating in the same geographical area (Becerra, 2008, p. 39).

es and developing group knowledge about opportunities. They also created social capital and suggested ways to overcome restrictions created by the divergence between the knowledge of individual entrepreneurs and aspects such as the contents of the program, work schedules or economic resources.

The structuring of internal and external networks, and the relationship between them, is essential to establishing a solid basis for the creation of shared value. This is principally because it is possible to draw on these networks to specify the particular conditions that increase participation levels. In this way members grew to enjoy greater access to information on available knowledge and experiences, to cooperate with other members of the network, to grow and increase their levels of responsiveness, ultimately promoting trust and social cohesion.

Through the theoretical and practical exercise conducted as a part of the *Emprende* project we found that there was reciprocity between internal and external networks (see Figure 5), particularly in the interaction between entrepreneurs' venues and the benefits obtained by the university community. As the program moved forward, the participation¹² of different academic areas within the university became more apparent,

12. The environment observation tool designed by Business Life, contributed to the participation of entrepreneurs with other members of the community, including competitors, suppliers, and others.

Photo 4. Strategic Business Model. Event 2: potential partners

Photo 5. Strategic Business Model. Event 2: potential customers

Figure 5. Internal and External Social Network

primarily through the network created with entrepreneurs to help them increase their knowledge and enhance their business models. Similarly, this paved the way for the creation of synergies between the different groups that made up the work teams, entrepreneurs and potential clusters, whose development was discussed at the beginning of the process.

An example of the relationship between networks and value chains in the case of entrepreneurs was provided by the university through the inclusion in the program of business plans presented by *Cintel*¹³ and *Shawarma*¹⁴.

Cintel geared its value proposal towards creating a competitive advantage, strengthening of a waste management culture, and responsible use of electronic devices. They also projected developing partnerships with the university's engineering department.

Shawarma, a carryout restaurant selling food from a window onto the street did not have a space where customers could eat comfortably and in hygienic conditions. This was their

13. *Cintel's* value proposal: "Cintel offers accessories and technical services for electronics repair, specializing in cellphones and tablets. It focuses its attention mainly on the university community, which uses the service on a daily basis. It provides security and confidence to its clients, providing advice and support during the purchase, use, maintenance and repair of the products. Aware of the environmental impact produced by both the parts and the devices, we seek support from the District Secretary of the Environment, CAR, and Eco-Compute in order to fulfil the four "Rs" governing the management of waste from cellphones and tablets: repair, reuse, recycle, and renovate", Universidad de los Andes, 2013.
14. *Shawarma's* value proposal: "Shawarma Rain & Sun is a fast food restaurant. Its preparations mix the delicacies of Middle Eastern food with the flavors of our region. Having limited space, and understanding the needs of students and workers, Shawarma Rain & Sun has created a unique venue providing well-balanced foods. It seeks to promote wellbeing by providing balanced meals for daily life, regardless of the weather and within 70 seconds. Counting on you, we offer Shawarma Sun and, on rainy days, we deliver Shawarma Rain", Universidad de los Andes, 2013.

motivation for joining the value proposal, which provides consumer spaces within the university, reducing the time people on campus need to expend buying food.

The three business models presented in the methodology, the practice sessions in class, the BL tool and, in particular, the events were all triggers that enhanced the capacity of the entrepreneurs and their businesses to cooperate with the university. Response capacity was facilitated by the openness and positive attitudes of some of the entrepreneurs, the recognition and attention that the team paid to their personal and commercial life stories, expectations, future vision, and perceptions about *Las Aguas* area. All of these aspects promoted self-confidence and empowered participating entrepreneurs to face new challenges.

Furthermore, the growing confidence of the entrepreneurs allowed them to partake in the work of others. This was particularly the case as the taking in of knowledge through the experience of the prototypes became a key strategy for creative work. By listening and asking questions, they explored possibilities, discovered alternatives, and recognized other perspectives. Their dialogue empowered their learning and action skills.

Within this scenario, the project achieved a sense of belonging in the program and we were able to share our ideals in a training process for entrepreneurs from the *Triángulo de Fenicia*, a community that had not previously been recognized as such.

CONCLUSIONS

Social innovation and people

As an entrepreneurship and competitiveness project, *Emprende* facilitated the interaction and characterization of the modes of operation of a community and its individuals, thus leading to practices that are key to social innovation. It functioned as an organic process in which people, work elements, and action related in ways that helped establish differential value in relation to existing situations in the business ecosystem.

The synergy developed between internal and external networks provided evidence of the existence of a replicable model of social innovation. Currently, the university is considering a second version of the program and a follow up of the venues included in the first phase in the hope of strengthening the program and being able to measure the results of the social innovation.

Methodology

Using a methodology based on design thinking helped to develop social innovation as individuals developed entrepreneurship skills, empowering themselves, their ideas, and their businesses (in a bottom-up process). Amongst the skills acquired by entrepreneurs the following may be highlighting: risk taking, teamwork, and tackling creative work.

Keeping in mind the working definition of shared value, the methodology was a key means for guiding entrepreneurs towards collaborative work and to develop their understanding of the business environment. Similarly, the creation of networks was the basis for promoting the creation of shared value and clusters.

The use of Business Life tools allowed us to visualize new scenarios for the business model and contributed to the formation of networks and work teams. In the same manner, the prototypes enabled ideas to gain recognition and results to be validated collectively.

Networks and shared value

The networks we identified enabled the participation of stakeholders from the community in social, entrepreneurial, and academic activities, thus creating synergy and strengthening partnerships. In this manner, networks captured and delivered value for businesses, helping them work towards the creation of competitive advantages, which benefited entrepreneurs and the university alike.

Clusters and potential replication

The creation of new external networks prompted the development of local clusters, which belong to a new dimension of interdependence. That is, local businesses developed new relationships with university institutions and their surrounding community, thus promoting an environment of opportunity for the growth of the overall community and the creation of wealth.

Shared value has enhanced the upward mobility of venues by helping them focus on the interests of the university and the needs of the community. Both horizontal and vertical networks balance the relationship between bottom-up and top-down processes of value creation.

Finally, the program provided an opportunity to create networks and shared value, the outcome of both processes being conducive to social innovation. The result was that the community of entrepreneurs from the *Triángulo de Fenicia* was transformed into a potential professional practice network, working to provide social and community development for all of its residents.

REFERENCES

Beckman S. & Barry M. (2007). *Innovation as a Learning Process: Embedding Design Thinking*. Beckley Haas School Business: University of California.

Becerra, F. (2008, July - December). Las redes empresariales y la dinámica de la empresa: aproximación teórica. *Innovar* [versión electrónica]. *Revista de Ciencias Administrativas y Sociales*. Universidad Nacional de Colombia, 18 (32), 27-45.

Beltrán, J., Londoño, S., Neira, C. & Raffo, A. (13 Diciembre 2013). "Study 4" class members report. https://sicuaplus.uniandes.edu.co/webapps/portal/frameset.jsp?tab_tab_group_id=_2_1&url=%2Fwebapps%2Fblackboard%2Fexecute%2Flauncher%3Ftype%3DCourse%26id%3D_35495_1%26url%3D Accessed 9th February 2014.

Daza, C. (producer) (2013). *Closing Video for Emprende*. Bogota: Media Workshop, Architecture and Design Faculties: https://sicuaplus.uniandes.edu.co/webapps/portal/frameset.jsp?tab_tab_group_id=_2_1&url=%2Fwebapps%2Fblackboard%2Fexecute%2Flauncher%3Ftype%3DCourse%26id%3D_35495_1%26url%3D Accessed 9th February 2014.

Dunne, D. & Martin, R. (2006). *Design Thinking and How It Will Change Management Education: An Interview and Discussion* [electronic version]. *Academy of Management Learning & Education*, 5(4), 512-523

Juarez, V. (2009). *Innovación social + Diseño estratégico*. México: Universidad Iberoamericana.

Kumar, V. (2013). *101 Design Methods. A Structured Approach for Driving Innovation in Your Organization*. New Jersey: John Wiley & Sons, Inc.

Landau, E. (1987). *El saber creativo, teoría y práctica e la creatividad*. Barcelona: Editorial Hender.

Murray, R., Caulier-Grice, J. & Mulgan, G. (2010). *Social Innovator Series: Ways to design, Develop and Grow Social Innovation*. The Open Book of Social Innovation. Nesta: The Young Foundation

Owen, C. (2005). *Design Thinking. What It is. Why It is Different. Where It Has New Value*. Illinois Institute of Technology: Institute of Design.

Porter, M. & Kramer (2011, Enero - Febrero.). *La creación de valor compartido*. Harvard Business School Publishing Corporation. *Review, América Latina*. Reimpresión R1101C-E

Silva, J. & Restrepo, S. (2013). *Explicación del proceso empresarial a partir del modelo Business life*. Bogotá. <http://businesslifemodel.com/#tools/cw4i>. Accessed 9th February 2014.

Restrepo, S. (2012). *Business Life: Creating Good Decisions* (Thesis). Bogotá: Universidad de los Andes

Universidad de los Andes (2013). *Informe Final Programa Emprende, Innovación en negocios. Resultados y evaluación*.

Walker, G., Kogut, B. & Shan, W. (199, March - April). *Social Capital, Structural Holes and the Formation of an Industry Network*. *Institute for Operations Research and the Management Science*, Vol. 8, No 2, 109-125.

Zapata, F. (2013). *Creatividad e innovación en modelos de negocio. Programa del curso Producto 4: Estrategia de Producto*. Bogotá: Universidad de los Andes. <http://designblog.uniandes.edu.co/blogs/dise2309/>. Accessed 9th February 2014.